

ТАШҚИ МУҲИТ ШАРОИТЛАРИГА ЮМШОҚ БУҒДОЙНИНГ МОСЛАШУВЧАНЛИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИ.

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INTRODUCTION. Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is the most important cereal crop in the world with an estimated area of more than 215 million hectares and a grain yield of more than 735 million tons (USDA (2020). *Global Agricultural Information Network*.). The population consumes 35 % of the grown wheat grain, which provides 29% of their energy needs. In recent years, as a result of climate change, wheat grain yields around the world have been adversely affected. This, in turn, makes the introduction of varieties with high adaptability to environmental conditions relevant.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the problem of water shortage observed in recent years makes it necessary to increase the yield of bread wheat. However, today, the breeding of bread wheat only for productivity reduces its genetic potential in adverse agro-climatic conditions.[1, 2]. The reason for this is that the varieties created and introduced into production have high productivity, but low resistance to adverse environmental conditions [3, 4]. In recent years, global warming has been reflected in agriculture. There are many scientific studies that support the scientific research that has been done and it is stated that this trend will continue until the end of this century [5, 6, 7]. One of the main indicators of adaptability is the study of periods of growth and development of introduced collection specimens in certain soil and climatic conditions [8]. L.V. Nazarenko pointed out that one of the factors affecting the yield and quality of wheat is growing conditions [9]. It is mainly carried out by increasing productivity and reducing losses under the influence of various stress factors. At the same time, the maximum use of the adaptability of varieties is one of the main tasks facing breeding, and in solving it, knowledge of the physiological characteristics of varieties under certain environmental conditions is of great importance [10].

MATERIALS AND METHODS. This study was conducted during 2017–2019 in the Tashkent region of Uzbekistan (41.2322°N and 69.2754°E). The experiments were conducted at the Dormon experimental site of the Institute of Genetics and Plant Experimental Biology. Wheat lines were planted in 5x60x10 m ring plots. When evaluating the physiological characteristics of the samples, more than 10 flag leaves were taken and analyzed from each line. Elite spring

wheat yield trial (38th ESWYT) used for the experiment from CIMMYT (Mexico) and Krasnodarskaya 99 was used as local check. To study the amount of chlorophyll "a", chlorophyll "b" and carotenoids in the leaves of wheat plants, each leaf by 50 milligrams was placed in a test tube. Each leaf sample was homogenized in 5 ml of 100% acetone solution. The homogenate was centrifuged for 10 min at 5,000 rpm. The light absorption values of chlorophyll "a", chlorophyll "b", total chlorophyll and carotenoids in the resulting extract were determined at 664, 645 and 470 nm (Agilent Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer). Based on this indicator, the amounts of chlorophyll "a", chlorophyll "b", total chlorophyll and carotenoids in the leaves of wheat were calculated using the equations Lichtentaler and Wellburn [11].

RESULTS. A high level of quantitative indicators during the period of grain ripening depends on the optimal level of physiological processes. Among other things, scientific articles mention that the amount of chlorophyll depends on valuable economic indicators from physiological processes. The scientific literature notes that high chlorophyll content can be used as a measure of wheat tolerance to high temperatures. It has been noted that genetically similar genotypes differ in changes in the amount of chlorophyll depending on the external environment and cultivation conditions, as well as a different response to external environmental influences. In the results of the analysis, it was observed that the amount of total chlorophyll varied over the years. The overall average value of the samples was $2,63 \pm 0,26$ mg/g. K-7 ($3,14 \pm 0,51$), K-13 ($2,87 \pm 0,11$), K-46 ($2,94 \pm 0,08$) and K-64 ($3,34 \pm 0,11$) samples were determined which performed above the overall average. It was observed that the content of carotenoids in the samples increased in accordance with high chlorophyll content.

Table-4

Indicators physiological and yield

Catalog number	chlorophyll, gr /mg	carotenoid, gr /mg	Net productivity of photosynthesis g /m ² . day.	TKW, gr	Grain yield c/ha
7	$3,14 \pm 0,51$	$2,02 \pm 0,07$	$6,25 \pm 0,35$	$48,0 \pm 0,56$	$70,7 \pm 3,15$
8	$2,55 \pm 0,18$	$1,68 \pm 0,09$	$4,26 \pm 0,38$	$45,9 \pm 1,27$	$65,6 \pm 7,16$
13	$2,87 \pm 0,11$	$1,87 \pm 0,31$	$6,36 \pm 0,56$	$48,2 \pm 2,04$	$71,6 \pm 4,29$
20	$2,45 \pm 0,28$	$1,74 \pm 0,17$	$5,21 \pm 0,37$	$45,3 \pm 1,18$	$65,4 \pm 6,98$
21	$2,66 \pm 0,37$	$1,65 \pm 0,15$	$5,31 \pm 0,65$	$46,5 \pm 1,33$	$66,6 \pm 3,86$

32	2,82±0,53	1,90±0,37	5,11±0,43	47,0±0,40	67,7±4,02
41	2,27±0,20	1,53±0,09	4,75±0,65	45,2±2,17	62,8±5,28
46	2,94±0,08	2,06±0,05	4,80±0,43	47,7±0,78	68,9±2,86
47	2,06±0,08	1,40±0,09	5,47±0,28	42,9±1,10	62,3±4,17
49	2,37±0,32	1,62±0,21	4,75±0,54	45,2±1,09	64,9±4,13
56	2,57±0,15	1,66±0,07	5,04±0,41	45,9±0,82	66,1±5,55
60	2,65±0,25	1,83±0,18	5,53±0,23	46,4±1,33	66,6±3,09
61	2,03±0,19	1,41±0,13	5,21±0,76	42,6±2,36	61,1±1,84
64	3,34±0,11	2,18±0,04	6,48±0,62	49,8±0,11	77,6±1,63
74	2,69±0,45	1,83±0,30	5,54±0,21	47,0±0,76	67,4±8,01
80	2,69±0,16	1,96±0,26	6,39±0,62	46,7±1,26	67,3±2,45
81	2,58±0,22	1,66±0,14	4,56±0,44	46,4±0,70	66,3±3,93
82	2,62±0,27	1,73±0,26	5,75±0,34	46,4±0,61	66,4±3,26
89	2,83±0,23	1,88±0,15	5,12±0,33	47,1±0,60	68,6±1,54
100	2,46±0,42	1,61±0,28	4,89±0,40	45,4±0,79	65,5±1,07
$\bar{x} \pm S_{\bar{x}}$	2,63±0,26	1,76±0,17	5,34±0,41	46,2±2,13	66,9±4,12

The samples with a high content of chlorophyll turned out to be more resistant to water deficit during the grain filling period, which led to an increase in valuable economic traits. The high content of chlorophyll can be used as criterion for wheat resistance to high temperatures and used in crop selection.

The accumulation of dry matter in bread wheat is one of the important parameters that determine the efficiency and productivity of photosynthesis. In our experiments, it was noted that the daily productivity of photosynthesis varied between the lowest 4,26±0,38 mg/g.day, and the highest 6,48±0,62 mg/g.day. Above average results were identified in K-7 (6,25±0,35), K-(6,36±0,56), K-64 (6,48±0,62) and K-80(6,39±0,62) samples (table 4). The lowest result was observed in the sample K-8 (4,26±0,38) and it was estimated that it was relatively resistant to water shortage. The reason for the resistance of these species was the depletion of the chlorophyll content in the leaves and the decrease in other physiological processes under water stress.

CONCLUSION

According to the results of the analysis of the K-7 (3,34±0,11), K-46 (2,94±0,08) and K-64 (3,14±0,51), with a high content of chlorophyll, high photosynthesis productivity K-7 (6,25±0,35), K-64 (6,48±0,62) samples were reviewed and it

was found that the grain is resistant to water deficit during the illing period and the yield increased.

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